

FigS4. Study of the cell-to-cell variability observed in the Snf1/Mig1 system.

Hxt7-GFP before and following a switch from ethanol media to media containing 220mM glucose. Time lapse microscopic images, upper images show HXT7-GFP, the lower images show brightfield.